

The Violence of the Empire in J.M. Coetzee's *Foe*: A Postcolonial Perspective

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 01, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Foe, Colonizer, Colonized, Contrapuntal Reading, Empire, Violence</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4904791</p>	<p><i>J.M. Coetzee is considered to be a prolific writer who has responded effectively to the dominant narrative in colonial discourse. In his works J.M. Coetzee has exposed the colonial machinations, which the colonizers used to subjugate the colonized people. In this sense, Postcolonial literature is a counter-discourse, which unearths the hidden underpinnings in the colonial discourse. To dismantle the 'master narratives', Edward Said's 'contrapuntal reading' (1993) is a useful technique to understand the various methods used by the colonists in their representations of the natives. Colonists have portrayed natives of the occupied territories as violent and wild people, who are to be controlled through aggressive means. This fabricated representation of the natives gives a solid reason to the colonizers to justify their atrocities in the colonized territory. Contrapuntal reading of Coetzee's <i>Foe</i> (1986) helps the readers identify the real perpetrators of the crimes in the colonized world. In this novel, Coetzee shows how the colonizers in the name of civilization commit the severest type of aggression in colonized regions to suppress the innocent natives. Coetzee in <i>Foe</i> shows violence of the Empire at such a scale that it deconstructs the dominant discourse of the colonizers that the natives in the occupied region are barbaric rather than it further reveals the barbaric face of the colonizers. An attempt has been made in this paper to read the continuities of oppression in postcolonized societies by taking <i>Foe</i> as a reference point for a particular kind of contrapuntal and postcolonial reading.</i></p>

Introduction

Postcolonial literature has occupied a great space in the domain of modern literature, it refers to literature published in English in formerly colonized nations (Ashcroft, Griffiths, & Tiffin, 1995). Thus, different types of theoretical concepts have emerged in this field. In this regard, many different writers have greatly contributed to the field by introducing various features, as Young has used the term 'Holy Trinity' for Said, Bhabha, and Spivak for introducing colonial discourse analysis as a discipline in academic circles (Young, 1995). Edward Said in *Orientalism* exposes the lies of the colonizers who have portrayed the natives of Africa as cannibals, when he says that there is a need to differentiate between 'truth' and 'representations' (Said, 1979). In *Culture and Imperialism* (1993) Said further suggests a type of reading which he calls 'contrapuntal reading' to unearth the colonial machinations of the Empire that how the forces of the Empire justified their violent acts in the name of civilization in different parts of the world.

According to Bonnici (2004), Coetzee's novels mainly contain a critique of colonialism and its effects and also the ethical and historical restraints on white writers. According to Attwell, (1993) in South Africa Coetzee is a regional writer. However, some of his novels are out of this category of the regional context, as Easton (1995) remarks about *Waiting for the Barbarians* (1980) that this novel is situated in non-specific place; and *Foe* (1986) is set on an unnamed island from where it moves to Bristol and different parts of England.

Statement of the Problem

In this famous novel *Foe*, J.M. Coetzee applies a certain type of reading that was named by Edward Said (1993) in his acclaimed book *Culture and Imperialism* as 'contrapuntal reading' of canonical European texts. Contrapuntal reading unearths the ideological underpinnings of the main canonical English texts like *Robinson Crusoe* that Coetzee directly counters in his highly multifaceted book *Foe*. It becomes essential to determine how Coetzee has tried to colour the happy canonical depiction of *Robinson Crusoe* with colonial pain in its all entirety. This pain is the foundational element in postcolonialism and leads to a practical struggle against colonialism and subjugation of the foreign lands. Furthermore, it becomes imperative to investigate how Coetzee has unearthed the disguised colonial machinations of the Empire in his prominent work *Foe*.

Literature Review

J.M. Coetzee, a white postcolonial writer, has exposed the terrible violence of the Empire against the natives of South Africa. His sympathy for the black natives is quite visible in his novels, which narrate the stories of atrocities of the Empire in South Africa. However, in spite of his sympathetic attitude towards the natives who were suffering in all spheres of their lives under the apartheid system, he admits the fact that he, being white, could not entirely absolve himself of the charges of the brutal treatment of the native population in South Africa. In his speech at Jerusalem Prize Acceptance Speech in 1987 (quoted by David, 1992:96) Coetzee expresses this type of feelings:

The masters in South Africa form a closed hereditary caste. Everyone born with a white skin is born into the caste. Since there is no way of escaping the skin you are born with (can the leopard change its spots?), you cannot resign from the caste. You can imagine resigning, you can perform a symbolic resignation, but, short of shaking the dust off your feet, there is no way of actually doing it.

Coetzee, being an eyewitness of the apartheid era, gives a detailed account of violence practiced during the time of apartheid administration. White colonizers resorted to the worst form of oppression against the natives to colonize them completely. According to Moore (2008), racist connotations of colonialism is very much explicit in practice as the structure of colonialism was completely dictatorial. It often resorted to violence to subdue its subjects to maintain law and order situation. Everything was in control of the colonial officers because in London the British Colonial Office would make all the decisions regarding the colonies. Colonizers often work on the assumption that they were superior to the natives Africa due to such a notion they considered it their right to control and exploit all the resources of the Africans in the name of civilization. Moore has aptly remarked about this policy of the colonizers that it is a contradiction in terms for the occupying forces to usher in civilization. Colonial forces also established the apartheid system in Africa to segregate the population into superior and inferior groups. It was the system thought to be the most horrible type of minority rule in South Africa, which often used violent strategies against blacks. The white forces of the Empire arrested, brutally tortured, and gruesomely murdered the innocent black males, females, and children. South Africa witnessed violence in various forms at different levels that resulted in the decolonization of the region as Fanon (quoted by Gerry Turcotte) stated that decolonization destroyed both the colonizers and the colonized, as a result, it would give space to a new kind of humanity (Lopez, 2012).

During the time of colonization, there were regular clashes between the colonizers and the native population. According to Said (1979), the colonizers often represented the native people as degenerate, antidemocratic, barbaric, backward, and so forth to justify their occupation. Said further writes in *Orientalism* about such type of exterior representation that it is not true rather a fabricated story about the colonized. Such representation provides a good pretext to the colonial authorities to subdue these natives by use of force. The colonized are represented as uncivilized people who are to be civilized. To carry out their mission of occupying the foreign territories, colonizers would often resort to brute force to control the local population. Reading Coetzee's *Foe* contrapuntally reveals oppression of the Empire in the occupied territory. Such occupation of the colonized lands is characterized by bloodshed, cruel rule, state aggression, and genocide of the native population by the forces of the Empire.

Coetzee reveals the malevolent intentions of the Empire, which remains fully involved in the worst form of oppression against the native Africans. Coetzee holds the Empire responsible for its aggressive policies, which provoke the feelings of insurgency in the colonized people. It is seen that the natives express their staunch reaction against the brutal policies of the Empire in various forms. Ania Loomba (1998) a postcolonial critic, said that in various parts of the world colonialism existed in different forms but everywhere it brought the colonizers and the colonized into the most complicated and traumatic relationships.

Here, it becomes necessary to examine the main ideology of colonial institutions to understand their vicious designs. Colonial masters occupy foreign territories to increase their dominions. Though, colonial forces claim that they occupy other regions to civilize the uncivilized people but in reality, it is their colonial agenda to grasp the land and its resources by using force in different forms and manifestations. The natives fight for their indigenous rights and freedom against the colonial forces that result in confrontation. Such type of confrontation between the colonizers and the colonized gives space to violence.

The colonial authorities often employed violent strategies to oppress the colonized because they believed that the use of aggression is the only way to subdue the native population. As Daniel Defoe in his work *Robinson Crusoe* presents the native Africans as cannibals when Robinson Crusoe (1994) (the narrator) expressed his apprehensions that he had heard that the native inhabitants, living on the Caribbean coast, were known to be cannibals or man-eaters. He further feared that even if they were not cannibals still they might kill him as in the past these (native inhabitants) had killed the European people and afterward consumed their dead bodies as their meal. Joseph Conrad (2005) also represents Africans as cannibals in *Heart of Darkness*, when Marlow, the narrator, calls them "Fine fellows--cannibals" (p.41). By representing them as cannibals, the Europeans found the pretext to adopt the violent means of subjugation against the natives in the name of civilization.

In the beginning days of colonization, the native inhabitants of the African territory were not fully acquainted with the evil intentions of the colonizers. They remained completely subordinate to the colonizers in all fields. But after some time the native people started realizing that the colonizers had come to their land as intruders to overpower them and take hold of all their natural resources, so they started passive resistance against their nasty designs. Sartre (2004) in his preface to *The Wretched of the Earth* (2004) said that the yellow and black voices still reckoned to humanism but they blamed the colonizers for their inhumanity. After understanding the imperialist designs of the occupying forces, who had come to the region to enslave the native people, the African natives showed their disobedience to the 'white' masters. The natives wanted to liberate their motherland from the occupying forces that consequently led to violent confrontations between the 'white' and the 'black'. Sartre was of the view that the young population of Africa was no more frightened of the colonial forces who had scared their elders by using brutal force against these native elders to subdue them. The young natives showed a staunch resistance to the horrible policies of the Empire.

To explore the negative effects of colonialism on the minds of the natives, Nandy (1983) in *Intimate Enemy Loss and Recovery of Self under Colonialism* said that the sources of colonialism were deeply embedded in the minds of the colonizers and the colonized. Colonialism is a state of mind that has started in the minds of the people and must end in the minds of the people.

Theoretical and Methodological Framework

Postcolonial theory is employed as a theoretical framework to analyse the selected text. It is extremely useful for comprehending the subtle re-reading of colonial literary text *Robinson Crusoe* that Coetzee has responded to in the context of his much-admired work *Foe*. This framework provides us the tools to highlight the strains and tensions that postcolonial reading registers in analysis of the colonial texts.

The research study is qualitative in nature. Qualitative research is a broad term that encapsulates several types of research practices and techniques. It is a wide and comprehensively evolving methodological field that includes a variety of approaches used in different types of research works from several perspectives.

The text under study is analyzed through a descriptive and interpretivist approach. The application of interpretivist techniques is a very much useful strategy to view the hidden ideologies/discourses in the text. Textual analysis is described to be a systematic and well-organized approach used in a descriptive study.

Analysis and Discussion

Coetzee's seminal work *Foe* reveals the barbaric acts of the Empire in the name of civilization in the African continent. Using civilization as a facade, the Empire brought the colonized natives in the African continent under its control through oppressive means and further snatched all their resources. The Empire used all types of brutal methods to subjugate the natives who were terribly tortured and also rendered them voiceless by suppressing their language. Fanon narrates such cruel acts of the colonizers in his famous work *Wretched of the Earth* (2004), where an Algerian student narrates the story of the brutal killing of his mother by a French soldier who also took this Algerian student's two sisters to the barracks. This Algerian student did not know anything about them till last. He was dreadfully shaken by his mother's death. It is one of the examples of the barbaric acts of the Empire out of numerous ones. The violence of the Empire is quite loud and clear in *Foe*. Susan Barton, in the novel, reckons to the atrocities of the Empire that uses barbaric ways to subdue the native Africans by mutilating their bodies with terrible instrument. She narrates the violence of the Empire in such words:

Indeed, it was the very secretness of his loss that caused me to shrink from him. I could not speak, while he was about, without being aware how lively were the movements of the tongue in my own mouth. I saw pictures in my mind of pincers gripping his tongue and a knife slicing into it, as must have happened, and I shuddered. (Coetzee, 1986, p. 24)

Here, Susan Barton describes the gruesome violence of the Empire that how categorically the forces of the Empire commit brutalities in the occupied territory by mutilating the bodies of the natives. The Empire inflicts deep wounds on the natives, which are caused in so a tactful manner that they are invisible to every eye, so that the world should not witness the violent acts of the Empire. As Susan Barton describes the wound of Friday to be secret and which is closed behind his lips. This is the real face of the civilized Empire that is involved in aggression in a sophisticated manner that it gives a permanent damage to the colonized without being noticed by common people. Question may arise what kind of civilization it is where humanity is being insulted to the level that human beings are turned into animals. Crusoe calls these natives as cannibals but he ignores his own cannibalism by snatching out the tongue of poor Friday to suppress his voice. Susan Barton tries to imagine the act of cutting of Friday's tongue that is even horrendous to imagine that how Friday's tongue must have been gripped in pincers and then a sharp blade must have cut it into pieces. Nobody in the world will fail to call it an act of extreme violence, where a living human being is mutilated gruesomely. This is really the worst type of aggression of the colonizers, who want to subdue the native population of the colonized territory. It is a clear evidence that colonization has been characterized by extreme violence of the Empire.

Susan Barton reveals the tyrannical oppression of her Empire, which is involved in extreme form of barbarism in the process of colonization of the land of Africa. She enumerates number of different heinous methods, which the Empire is used to employing to control the natives of the occupied territory. Though, apparently she discusses, such methods in question form, in reality these are truly colonial machinations to control the native population of the land. The Empire uses all possible means of violence to bring the region under its domination. Though, Cruso tells her that Friday's tongue has been cut by the slavers, still she does not believe in his version because she knows all the oppressive strategies adopted by her Empire in order to suppress the voice of the natives. Her questions are related to Cruso that it was he who had cut Friday's tongue so that he (Friday) should not tell the world the stories of atrocities of the Empire. She rejects the version of Cruso that these are the slavers who had cut Friday's tongue when she implicates Cruso in the crime while talking to Friday:

Your master says the slavers cut it out; but I have never heard of such a practice, nor did I ever meet a slave in Brazil who was dumb. Is the truth that your master cut it out himself and blamed the slavers? If so it was truly an unnatural crime, like chancing upon a stranger and slaying him for no other cause than to keep him from telling the world who slew him. (Coetzee, 1986, p. 84)

Here, she tells the real stories of violence, which her Empire had carried out in African region. Though, the popular slogan of the Empire is civilization, it has a facade of civility that it has come to Africa to civilize the native Africans through civilized means, but the actual story is different from it. The Empire does not want that the record of its barbarism should reach outside world. To conceal all its crimes from the world it resorts to the worst form of aggression in order to suppress the voice of the natives. Questions arise why the Empire does such type of brutality to the Africans who are harmless creatures living on their own land without harbouring any sort of dangerous design against the world at large. Rather it is the Empire that comes to their land as an intruder to occupy their land and its hidden resources in form of expensive minerals lying under African land.

Coetzee reveals the violence of the Empire in different forms and manifestations. Cruso, a symbol of Empire, cuts Friday's tongue and then uses him as an object of entertainment for his own amusement. He has made him his full-time servant, he uses him the way he wants irrespective of the fact that Friday is too a human being. As to amuse his Mistress Barton, he orders Friday, "Sing, Friday," and repeats, "Sing for Mistress Barton" (Coetzee, 1986, p. 22). Cruso forces him to sing despite the fact he has cut his tongue. It connotes the extreme violence of the Empire. Cruso commands Friday to sing and produce the sound, "La-la-la," which can only be produced with tongue but Cruso still forces him to produce it. Friday, despite his efforts, fails to produce it rather he makes, "Ha-ha-ha", due to mutilation of his tongue which is an important articulator of speech sound in a language (Coetzee, 1986, p. 22). Violence of Cruso is revealed at its extreme, when Susan Barton asks him the reason that why Friday cannot produce sound like 'la-la-la', he grips Friday by the hair and brings his face close to her to show her that Friday has no tongue. Gripping Friday by his hair is a testimony of inhuman treatment meted out to the indigenous people of African continent. This is a great insult of humanity when a living human being has been deprived of his voice to render him slave. Coetzee in *Foe* epitomizes the violence of the Empire to such an extent that it deprived the colonized of expressing their pain in humanly manner.

Conclusion

Contrapuntal reading of Coetzee's *Foe* reveals the tyrannical rule of the Empire in the African continent. The novel describes the violence of the Empire on a greater scale. The text is replete with scenes of violence of the Empire and its mutilations of the natives. The freedom of the natives is snatched from the natives who are subjected to the tyrannical rule of the Empire. Friday, who symbolizes the natives of Africa, becomes the victim of brutality of the Empire, symbolized by Cruso. To colonizers in Africa, the natives were cannibals who could only be controlled through violent means. The natives were excluded from the ambit of civilization due to their dark skin which the Empire considered cause of all evils in this world. Susan Barton's reference to the violent acts of her Empire in different parts of the novel reveals the crimes of the colonizers who remained involved in the worst type of atrocities in the region. In *Foe*, Coetzee reveals the colonial underpinnings that are employed to subjugate the native people of the Africa region. The irony is that these brutal acts are carried out by the Empire in the name of civilization, which is explicitly contradicted by its practices on the ground by using uncivilized means to subdue the natives. Coetzee very aptly exposes the barbaric face of the Empire in *Foe* when he shows the traumatic relationship between the colonizers and colonized.

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